

Basin Research

Supporting information for

Present and past thermal regime in the Northern Andes. Did the Farallon plate breakup play a role in the thermal history of the region?

González Román^{1,2,3,*}, Robert Ondrak, Eliseo Tesón, Andrés Mora³, Iván Camilo Higuera³, and Onno Oncken^{1,2}

¹GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences, Lithosphere Dynamics, Potsdam, Germany. ²Freie Universität Berlin, Department of Earth Sciences, Berlin, Germany. ³Ecopetrol, Bogotá, Colombia.

Supplemental Material

List of figures

Figure S1. Compilation of main tectonic events affecting the northwestern corner of South America.

Figure S2. Average thermal conductivity maps estimated for the stratigraphic layers of reference.

Figure S3. Stratigraphic thickness maps for the stratigraphic layers of reference.

Figure S4. Correlation functions between corrected thermal gradients and different thicknesses in the sedimentary sequence.

List of tables

Table S1. Correction of Bottom hole temperatures (BHT) for the Llanos Basin and Middle Magdalena Valley.

Table S2. Dataset of vitrinite reflectance measurements taken from previous studies.

Table S3. Stratigraphic framework and proposed heat flow history used in the simplified basin models presented in this study.

Table S4. Thermal parameters employed in the proposed thermal model.

Figure S1. Compilation of main tectonic events affecting the northwestern corner of South America. Events taken from González et al. (2023, 2025) and references therein.

Figure S2. Average thermal conductivity maps estimated in this study for the six stratigraphic layers of reference. These maps result from the simulation in Petromod[®] according to the compaction history and conductivity values for the different lithological mixes.

Figure S2. Continued

Figure S2. Continued

Figure S3. Modeled stratigraphic thicknesses of the six layers used in this study.

Figure S3. Continued

Figure S3. Continued

Figure S4. Correlation between corrected thermal gradients and different thicknesses in the sedimentary sequence, which allows for a first order approximation of the thermal gradient distribution across the basins. a) Thermal gradient correlations for the Llanos Basin using the total sedimentary thickness and the thicknesses of the Miocene and Paleozoic sequences. Note that the correlation between thermal gradient and the Miocene thickness shows a good correlation in wells with thicker column, but it scatters in wells with lower thickness. The correlation with the Paleozoic thickness shows a diffuse trend that may not be recommended for thermal gradient predictions. The best fit in the Llanos Basin is obtained with the total sedimentary sequence. Predicted thermal gradients, as shown in the equation, produce a difference from the measured data with a standard deviation of 2.7. b) Thermal gradient correlations for the Middle Magdalena Valley using the total sedimentary thickness and the thicknesses of the Cenozoic and Miocene sequences. The best fit in the Middle Magdalena Valley is obtained with the Miocene sedimentary sequence. Predicted thermal gradients, as shown in the equation, produce a difference from the measured data with a standard deviation of 2.5.

(see dataset in supplemental file)

Table S1. *Correction of Bottom hole temperatures (BHT) for the Llanos Basin and Middle Magdalena Valley. Dataset of uncorrected BHT measurements taken from the Colombian Geological Service [https://datos.sgc.gov.co/datasets/bf871b71a6094ccd9979218e3440df5c_0, 16/10/2024]*

(see dataset in supplemental file)

Table S2. *Dataset of vitrinite reflectance measurements in Maastrichtian to Paleocene sedimentary rocks taken from previous studies (Duarte et al., 2012, 2013, 2014; Mora, 2007; Moretti et al., 2010; Ortiz et al., 2018; Pulido, 2001).*

Cordillera_Landazuri

Elevation (m): -700

Layer	Sublayer	top	base	thck	Eroded	start	End
Erosion						23	0
Neogene	Neog1	-700	-700	0	900	35	23
Paleogene	Paleog2	-700	-700	0	1000	55	38
	Paleog1	-700	-700	0	1040	68	55
Upper Cretaceous	U_Cret2	-700	530	1230	0	88	69
	U_Cret1	530	1430	900	0	98	88
Lower Cretaceous	L_Cret4	1430	2630	1200	0	105	98
	L_Cret3	2630	3730	1000	0	124	105
	L_Cret2	3730	4230	500	0	134	124
	L_Cret1	4230	4400	170	0	145	134
Jurassic	Jur	4400	6900	2500	0	160	146
Paleozoic	Pz	6900	6900	0	0	-	-

Proposed Heat Flow History

Age	100 Ma	65 Ma	50 Ma	35 Ma	25 Ma	16 Ma	4 Ma	0 Ma
Heat Flow (mW/m ²)	90	60	49	46	90	75	50	45

Cordillera_El Cerro-1

Elevation (m): -1067

Layer	Sublayer	top	base	thck	Eroded	start	End
Erosion						24	0
Neogene (faulted block)	Neog1	-1067	-1067	0	200	36	24
Paleogene (faulted block)	Paleog2	-1067	-1067	0	1500	48	36
	Paleog1	-1067	-17	1050	200	65	55
Upper Cretaceous (faulted block)	U_Cret2	-17	1286	1303	0	81	75
	U_Cret1	1286	1856	570	0	98	81
Lower Cretaceous (faulted block)	L_Cre4	1856	2426	570	0	102	98
	L_Cret3	2426	3196	770	0	110	102
Upper Cretaceous	U_Cret2	3196	3396	200	0	81	75
	U_Cret1	3396	3886	490	0	98	81
Lower Cretaceous	L_Cret4	3886	4426	540	0	102	98
	L_Cret3	4426	4966	540	0	110	102
	L_Cret2	4966	5393	427	0	120	116
	L_Cret1	5393	5773	380	0	130	120
Jurassic	Jur	5773	6273	500	0	140	130
Paleozoic	Pz	6273	6273	0	0	-	-

Proposed Heat Flow History

Age	100 Ma	65 Ma	50 Ma	35 Ma	25 Ma	16 Ma	4 Ma	0 Ma
Heat Flow (mW/m ²)	87	59	48	42	50	38	32	30

Table S3. Stratigraphic framework and proposed heat flow history used in the simplified basin models presented in this study. See locations in Figure 10 of the main manuscript. SS: sandstone, SLST: siltstone, SH: shale, LST: limestone.

Cordillera_Guaduas

Elevation (m): -407

Layer	Sublayer	top	base	thck	Eroded	start	End
Erosion						8	0
Neogene	Neog2	-407	593	150	200	23	8
	Neog1	593	743	1000	0	40	23
Erosion						45	40
Paleogene	Paleog2	793	1193	200	100	55	45
	Paleog1	1193	1593	400	50	60	57
Upper Cretaceous	U_Cret2	1593	2463	1120	0	80	60
	U_Cret1	2463	2963	150	0	95	80
Lower Cretaceous	L_Cret4	2963	3363	500	0	105	95
	L_Cret3	3363	4213	1050	0	115	105
	L_Cret2	4213	4463	200	0	120	115
	L_Cret1	4463	4663	200	0	130	120
Jurassic	Jur	4663	4883	200	0	140	130
Paleozoic	Pz	4883	4883	0	0	-	-

Proposed Heat Flow History

Age	100 Ma	65 Ma	50 Ma	35 Ma	25 Ma	16 Ma	4 Ma	0 Ma
Heat Flow (mW/m ²)	89	61	50	44	52	40	34	32

Cordillera_Socha

Elevation (m): -2500

Layer	Sublayer	top	base	thck	Eroded	start	End
Erosion						16	0
Neogene	Neog2	-2500	-2500	0	200	23	16
	Neog1	-2500	-2500	0	530	35	23
Paleogene	Paleog2	-2500	-2500	0	900	55	38
	Paleog1	-2500	-1900	600	1000	68	55
Upper Cretaceous	U_Cret2	-1900	-800	1100	0	88	69
	U_Cret1	-800	-110	690	0	98	88
Lower Cretaceous	L_Cret4	-110	730	840	0	105	98
	L_Cret3	730	1690	960	0	124	105
	L_Cret2	1690	2050	360	0	134	124
	L_Cret1	2050	2230	180	0	145	134
Jurassic	Jur	2230	2230	0	0	-	-
Paleozoic	Paleoz	2230	4730	2500	0	160	146

Proposed Heat Flow History

Age	100 Ma	65 Ma	50 Ma	35 Ma	25 Ma	16 Ma	4 Ma	0 Ma
Heat Flow (mW/m ²)	90	60	49	46	85	70	50	45

Table S3. Continued

Layer	Sublayer		Lithology of reference	Calculated Thermal Conductivity (W/m/K)			Radiogenic Heat			Heat capacity at 20°C (kcal/kg/K)
				min	max	mean	U	Th	K	
							(ppm)	(ppm)	(%)	
Neogene	Late Miocene - Recent	Llanos	40SS_20CGL_20SLST_20SH	1,435	2,183	1,605	1.97	5.62	1.7	0.2
		MMV	60SS_5CGL_20SLST_15SH				1.81	5.1	1.49	0.21
	Middle Miocene	Llanos	80SS_10SLST_10SH	1,451	2,444	1,967	1.61	4.5	1.41	0.21
		MMV	50SS_50SLST				1.65	4.25	1.15	0.21
	Oligocene - Early Miocene	Llanos	40SS_20SLST_40SH	1,217	2,005	1,639	8.52	6.8	1.72	0.22
		MMV	30SS_20SLST_50SH				2.64	8.05	1.94	0.21
Paleogene	Late Eocene	Llanos	70SS_30SH	1,218	2,318	2,093	2.02	6.05	1.72	0.2
		MMV	30SS_15SLST_55SH				2.73	8.4	2.02	0.21
	Paleocene	Llanos	80SS_20SH	0,041	2,286	1,722	1.78	5.2	1.58	0.2
		MMV	40SS_60SH				2.74	8.6	2.14	0.21
Late Cretaceous	Late Cretaceous	Llanos	40SS_10SLST_50SH	1,044	2,052	1,892	2.57	7.9	1.97	0.21
		MMV	90SH_10LST				3.53	11.2	2.53	0.21
Early Cretaceous	Early Cretaceous	Llanos	10SS_80SH_10LST(shaly)	1,149	1,919	1,819	2.51	6.4	1.51	0.2
		MMV	80SH_20LST				3.25	10.1	2.28	0.21
Jurassic	Jurassic	MMV	60SS_40SH	1,536	2,26	2,113	2.26	6.9	1.86	0.2
Paleozoic	Paleozoic	Llanos	10SS_10SLST_80SH	1,366	1,882	1,705	3.29	10.45	2.39	0.21

Table S4. Thermal parameters employed in the proposed thermal model by using the reference values considering the Petromod[®] libraries. The calculated thermal conductivity values are variable properties that depend on the lithology mixtures and compaction histories across the basins (Figure S2). The thermal conductivity of the entire sedimentary succession shown in Figure 6b of the main manuscript is estimated as a thickness-weighted average of the individual stratigraphic units (Figure S3). SS: sandstone, SLST: siltstone, SH: shale, LST: limestone. MMV: Middle Magdalena Valley.

References

- Alfaro, C., Alvarado, I., & Manrique, A. (2015). Heat flow evaluation at Eastern Llanos sedimentary basin, Colombia. 34, 1-9.
- Duarte, C., Monroy, W., & Rincón, M. (2012). Exploración Gas Metano asociado al carbón. Área Lenguaque. Sector GMAC Boquerón de Tausa-La Pluma, Cucunubá (Proyecto SUB 09 - 24). Servicio Geológico Colombiano. <https://recordcenter.sgc.gov.co/B9/22004001024496/documento/pdf/2105244961101000.pdf>
- Duarte, C., Parra, F., & Rincón, M. (2014). Exploración Gas Metano asociado al Carbón. Área Tasco-Socotá. Servicio Geológico Colombiano. <https://recordcenter.sgc.gov.co/B9/22004002524678/documento/pdf/2105246781101000.pdf>
- Duarte, C., Rincón, M., & Parra, F. (2013). Exploración Gas Metano asociado al carbón. Área Chequa-Lenguaque. Guachetá-Samacá. Servicio Geológico Colombiano. <https://recordcenter.sgc.gov.co/B9/22004001024621/documento/pdf/2105246211101000.pdf>
- Mora, A. (2007). Inversion tectonics and exhumation processes in the Eastern Cordillera of Colombia. Thesis. Universität Potsdam.
- Moretti, I., Charry, G. R., Morales, M. M., & Mondragon, J. C. (2010). Integrated exploration workflow in the south Middle Magdalena Valley (Colombia). *Journal of South American Earth Sciences*, 29(2), 187-197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsames.2009.08.011>
- Ortiz, L., Parra, F., Duarte, C., & Rincón, M. (2018). Exploración de Gas Metano asociado al carbón. Área Guaduas-Caparrapí. Valle Medio del Magdalena. Departamento de Cundinamarca. Servicio Geológico Colombiano. https://recordcenter.sgc.gov.co/B23/554_18Exp_GMAC2017/Documento/Pdf/INFORME_GMAC_2017.pdf
- Pulido, O. (2001). Mapa del Potencial y rango del carbón. Plancha 5-06. Ingeominas. <https://recordcenter.sgc.gov.co/B5/13011050002511/documento/pdf/0101025111101000.pdf>
- Servicio Geológico Colombiano. Dataset of uncorrected BHT measurements in Colombian basins [https://datos.sgc.gov.co/datasets/bf871b71a6094ccd9979218e3440df5c_0, 16/10/2024].